

Milestone: M1.1 Project Mobilised

Lead Participant: ELIXIR Hub

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Due: 30 April 2024 (M3)

Date Of Completion: 6/05/2024

Means of Verification

Since the start of the project, regular meetings have been taking place, including monthly meetings of the Managing Board and WPs and quarterly ELIXIR-STEERS HoN meetings.

- Managing Board meeting minutes
 - [3rd March 2024](#)
 - [4th April 2024](#)

The first quarterly ELIXIR-STEERS HoN meeting is due to take place in May 2024.

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Delayed by 1 week due to review process

Project participants & others

ELIXIR Hub, WP Leaders, all STEERS project partners

Next action steps

N/A

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